

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-73-IC-1% 05 rac	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	
Vial:	56	Acq. Method Set:	1% 210400 05
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	LRM 4 73
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	290.0nm
Run Time:	20.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 290.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	3/6/2023 20:43:06 CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 16:30:47 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	9.419	912068	3.76	20956
2	11.085	11235773	46.32	318650
3	12.846	11217430	46.25	335673
4	14.000	889396	3.67	22494

SAMPLE INFORMATION

Sample Name:	LRM-4-71-IC-1% 05 asy	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name	20230306
Vial:	34	Acq. Method Set:	1% 210400 05
Injection #:	1	Processing Method	LRM 4 71
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	290.0nm
Run Time:	20.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 290.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	3/6/2023 19:48:20 CST		
Date Processed:	3/8/2023 16:34:08 CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	9.531	3755	0.13	143
2	11.295	24016	0.84	671
3	13.112	2821726	98.64	76595
4	14.253	11128	0.39	604